

Supplementary File S1. Multiple sequence alignment (ClustalW) of individual 16S rRNA amplicon sequencing reads (n = 11; 0.12% relative abundance) from cheese sample A10 that were assigned to *Paucilactobacillus kaifaensis* taxon aligned to the 16S rRNA full length sequence of *P. wasatchensis* WDC04 (NR_147709.1) and *P. kaifaensis* 778-3 (NR_179293.1).

16s rRNA variants between *P. wasatchensis* WDC04 (NR147709.1) and *P. kaifaensis* 778-3 (NR179293.1).

Position	82	94	102	104	267	275	303	305	313	832	880	1317
NR147709.1	C	C	G	G	T	C	G	A	A	C	G	A
NR179293.1	A	T	T	A	C	T	A	G	G	G	A	G
Position	15	27	35	37	200	208	236	238	246	765	813	1250

16S rRNA amplicon sequencing reads had poor sequence quality on the 5' end (prior to position 150) which resulted in poor alignment and a lack in confidence of the exact position assignment within the alignment.

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NR_147709.1  GA-TTG-ACGGTGCTTGCACCAGATTGAGAGAACATTTGAATG--AGTGG
NR_179293.1  GA-TTG-AAGGTGCTTGCCTAGATTGATAAACATTTGAATG--AGTGG
read120      CA-TTG-ACGGTGCTTGCACCAGATTGAGAGAACATTTGAATG--AGTGG
read1243     GAATTC-A-AGTGCTTGCACCAGATTGAGAGAACATTTGAATG--AGTGG
read3510     TA-C-T-ACGTGGCT--TACCAAATTCAGAGAACATTTGAATG--ATGAG
read3632     GA-TTG-ACGGCGCTTGGCACTGATCGAGAAACATTTGAATG--AGTGG
read3687     GA-TTG-ACGGTGCTTGCACCAGATTGAGAGAACATTTGAATG--AGTGG
read4670     TATTTG-ACTGGGA--GTATTATTGAGATAAAATATTTGAAGGAGAGTGG
read4730     GATTTGAATGGTGCTTGCACCAGATTGAGAGAACATTTGAATG--AGTGG
read5044     TT-T-T-TTTTTTTT---TTT---TTTT---TTTTTTTTTTTT---TCTGG
read6761     GA-TTG-ACGGTGCTTGCACCAGATTGAGAGAACATTTGAATG--AGTGG
read9384     GA-TTG-ACGGTGCTTGCACCAGATTGAGAGAACATTTGAATG--AGTGG
read9486     GA-TTG-ACAGTACT-GCAC-GGAT---GAGAACATTTGAATG--AGTG-
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NR_147709.1  TGATTTAAAAGATGGCCTTGTGCTATCACTTTTGGATGGATCCGCGGTGT
NR_179293.1  TGATTTAAAAGATGGCCTTGTGCTATCACTTTTGGATGGATCCGCGCGT
read120      TGATTTAA-AGATGGCCTTGTGCTATCACTTTTGGATGGATCCGCGGTGT
read1243     TGATTTAAAAGATGGCCTTGTGCTATCACTTTTGGATGGATCCGCGGTGT
read3510     TGATTTAAAAGATGGCCTTGTGCTATCACTTTTGGATGGATCCGCGGTGT
read3632     TGATTTAAATG-TG----CTGTTATCACTTTTGGATGGATCCGCGGTGT
read3687     TGATTTAAAAGATGGCCTTGTGCTATCACTTTTGGATGGATCCGCGGTGT
read4670     TGATTTAAAAGATGGCCTTGTGCTATCACTTTTGGATGGATCCGCGGTGT
read4730     TGATTTAAAAGATGGCCTTGTGCTATCACTTTTGGATGGATCCGCGGTGT
read5044     TGATTTAAAAGATGGCCTTGTGCTATCACTTTTGGATGGATCCGCGGTGT
read6761     TGATTTAAAAGATGGCCTTGTGCTATCACTTTTGGATGGATCCGCGGTGT
read9384     TGATTTAAAAGATGGCCTTGTGCTATCACTTTTGGATGGATCCGCGGTGT
read9486     TGATTTAAAAGATGGCCTTGTGCTATCACTTTTGGATGGATCCGCGGTGT
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NR_147709.1  ATTAGCTAGTTGGTAAGGTAAGGCTTACCAAGGCAATGATACATAGCCG
NR_179293.1  ATTAGTTAGTTGGTAAGGTAAGGCTTACCAAGACGATGATACGTAGCCG
read120      ATTAGCTAGTTGGTAAGGTAAGGCTTACCAAGGCAATGATACATAGCCG
read1243     ATTAGCTAGTTGGTAAGGTAAGGCTTACCAAGGCAATGATACATAGCCG
read3510     ATTAGCTAGTTGGTAAGGTAAGGCTTACCAAGGCAATGATACATAGCCG
read3632     ATTAGCTAGTTGGTAAGGTAAGGCTTACCAGGGCAATGATACATAGCCG
read3687     ATTAGCTAGTTGGTAAGGTAAGGCTTACCAAGGCAATGATACATAGCCG
read4670     ATTAGCTAGTTGGTAAGGTAAGGCTTACCAAGGAACT--TACATAGCCG
read4730     ATTAGCTAGTTGGTAAGGTAAGGCTTACCAAGGCAATGATACATGGCCG
read5044     ATTAGCTAGTTGGTAAGGTA--GGCTTACCAAGGCAATGATACATAGCCG
read6761     ATTAGCTAGTTGGTAAGGTAAGGCTTACCAAGGCAATGATACATAGCCG
read9384     ATTAGCTAGTTGGTAAGGTAAGGCTTACCAAGGCAATGATACATAGCCG
read9486     ATTAGCTAGTTGGTAAGGTAAGGCTTACCAAGGCAATGATACATAGCCG
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NR_147709.1 GAACAGGATTAGATACCCTGGTAGTCCATGCCGTA AACGATGAATGCTAG
NR_179293.1 GAACAGGATTAGATACCCTGGTAGTCCATGCCGTA AACGATGAATGCTAG
read120 GAACAGGATTAGATACCCTGGTAGTCCATGCCGTA AACGATGAATGCTAG
read1243 GAACAGGATTAGATACCCTGGTAGTCCATGCCGTA AACGATGAATGCTAG
read3510 GAACAGGATTAGATACCCTGGTAGTCCATGCCGTA AACGATGAATGCTAG
read3632 GAACAGGATTAGATACCCTGGTAGTCCATGCCGTA AACGATGAATGCTAG
read3687 GAACAGGATTAGATACCCTGGTAGTCCATGCCGTA AACGATGAATGCTAG
read4670 GAACAGGATTAGATACCCTGGTAGTCCATGCCGTA AACGATGAATGCTAG
read4730 GAACAGGATTAGATACCCTGGTAGTCCATGCCGTA AACGATGAATGCTAG
read5044 GAACAGGATTAGATACCCTGGTAGTCCATGCCGTA AACGATGAATGCTAG
read6761 GAACAGGATTAGATACCCTGGTAGTCCATGCCGTA AACGATGAATGCTAG
read9384 GAACAGGATTAGATACCCTGGTAGTCCATGCCGTA AACGATGAATGCTAG
read9486 GAACAGA—TAGATACCCTGGTAGTCCATGCCGTA AACGATGAATGCTAG
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832

NR_147709.1 GTGTTGGAGGGTTTCCGCCCTTGGTGCCGCAGCTAACGCATTAAGCATT
NR_179293.1 GTGTTGGAGGGTTTCCGCCCTTGGTGCCGCAGCTAACGCATTAAGCATT
read120 GTGTTGGAGGGTTTCCGCCCTTGGTGCCGCAGCTAACGCATTAAGCATT
read1243 GTGTTGGAGGGTTTCCGCCCTTGGTGCCGCAGCTAACGCATTAAGCATT
read3510 GTGTTGGAGGGTTTCCGCCCTTGGTGCCGCAGCTAACGCATTAAGCATT
read3632 GTGTTGGAGGGTTTCCGCCCTTGGTGCCGCAGCTAACGCATTAAGCATT
read3687 GTGTTGGAGGGTTTCCGCCCTTGGTGCCGCAGCTAACGCATTAAGCATT
read4670 GTGTTGGAGGGTTTCCGCCCTTGGTGCCGCAGCTAACGCATTAAGCATT
read4730 GTGTTGGAGGGTTTCCGCCCTTGGTGCCGCAGCTAACGCATTAAGCATT
read5044 GTGTTGGAGGGTTTCCGCCCTTGGTGCCGCAGCTAACGCATTAAGCATT
read6761 GTGTTGGAGGGTTTCCGCCCTTGGTGCCGCAGCTAACGCATTAAGCATT
read9384 GTGTTGGAGGGTTTCCGCCCTTGGTGCCGCAGCTAACGCATTAAGCATT
read9486 GTGTTGGAGGGTTTCCGCCCTTGGTGCCGCAGCTAACGCATTAAGCATT
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880

NR_147709.1 GTAAGCTAATCTCTTAAAACCGTTCTCAGTTCGGACTGTAGGCTGCAACT
NR_179293.1 GTAAGCTAATCTCTTAAAACCGTTCTCAGTTCGGACTGTAGGCTGCAACT
read120 GTAAGCTAATCTCTTAAAACCGTTCTCAGTTCGGACTGTAGGCTGCAACT
read1243 GTAAGCTAATCTCTTAAAACCGTTCTCAGTTCGGACTGTAGGCTGCAACT
read3510 GTAAGCTAATCTCTTAAAACCGTTCTCAGTTCGGACTGTAGGCTGCAACT
read3632 GTAAGCTAATCTCTTAAAACCGTTCTCAGTTCGGACTGTAGGCTGCAACT
read3687 GTAAGCTAATCTCTTAAAACCGTTCTCAGTTCGGACTGTAGGCTGCAACT
read4670 GTAAGCTAATCTCTTAAAACCGTTCTCAGTTCGGACT—AGGCTGCAACT
read4730 GTAAGCTAATCTCTTAAAACCGTTCTCAGTTCGGACTGTAGGCTGCAACT
read5044 GTAAGCTAATCTCTTAAAACCGTTCTCAGTTCGGACTGTAGGCTGCAACT
read6761 GTAAGCTAATCTCTTAAAACCGTTCTCAGTTCGGACTGTAGGCTGCAACT
read9384 GTAAGCTAATCTCTTAAAACCGTTCTCAGTTCGGACTGTAGGCTGCAACT
read9486 GTAAGCTAATCTCTTAAAACCGTTCTCAGTTCGGACTGTAGGCTGCAACT
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